

Descriptor: *Forward-Looking Multibeam—Marine Litter Detection and Tracking Dataset (FLM-MLDT)*

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This work was supported by the National Funds through the Portuguese funding agency, Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT) with the Studentship for Doctoral Research Funding Programme with the DOI <https://doi.org/10.54499/SFRH/BD/151460/2021>, the project UID/50014/2025 with the DOI <https://doi.org/10.54499/UID/50014/2025>, and the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, under Grant 101112812 (NETTAG+).

ABSTRACT Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science (INESC TEC) aims to make a significant contribution to the advancement of marine robotics and environmental monitoring by providing a novel dataset: the Forward-Looking Multibeam—Marine Litter Detection and Tracking Dataset (FLM-MLDT). Addressing the critical scarcity of labelled underwater data, this work presents 8156 acoustic images acquired using the Kongsberg M3 High-Frequency Multibeam Echosounder with a forward-looking configuration installed in the PORTUS Unmanned Surface Vehicle (USV). Collected in the manoeuvring basin of Leixões harbour, this dataset offers information on ten distinct types of marine debris. It provides input for developing deep learning algorithms, refining sonar signal processing, and enhancing the perception capabilities of different platforms for data extraction and environmental interaction. To ensure immediate utility and reliability, the dataset provides baseline metrics established using the You Only Look Once version 8 (YOLOv8) detector. By making this dataset publicly available, INESC TEC seeks to drive further innovation in underwater computer vision and automated clean-up solutions, fostering a cleaner and more sustainable ocean environment.

IEEE SOCIETY/COUNCIL IEEE Oceanic Engineering Society (OES)

DATA TYPE/LOCATION Multibeam echosounder acoustic images; Manoeuvring basin of Leixões harbour, Porto, Portugal

DATA DOI/PID 10.5281/zenodo.18235788

INDEX TERMS Acoustic imaging, marine litter, multibeam echosounder (MBES), perception, sonar, sustainability, underwater, unmanned surface vehicle (USV), water column data.

BACKGROUND

Public datasets on marine litter detection can be extremely useful for various reasons related to ecosystem preservation and robotic intervention, including environmental monitoring, automated clean-up and integration of autonomous systems. The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP)

defines marine litter as any persistent, manufactured, or processed solid material discarded in the marine environment [1], [2], [3]. With an estimated 53 million tonnes of plastic projected to enter the oceans annually by 2030 [4], having comprehensive and reliable datasets on underwater debris could significantly improve our ability to manage and

FIG. 1. Aerial view of the manoeuvring basin of Leixões harbour (Porto, Portugal) where the dataset campaign took place.

FIG. 2. PORTUS USV deployed in the manoeuvring basin of Leixões harbour.

mitigate this threat. This could lead to more efficient and sustainable robotic clean-up systems that can effectively handle submerged litter before it fragments into microplastics [2], reducing potential global damage.

The continued development of autonomous monitoring has prompted further inspection into the capabilities of underwater sensors to detect debris in the water column. This is most prevalent in turbid coastal areas, ports, or high-traffic routes where optical sensors fail. Although data from surface observations (satellites, drones) are available [4], very few if any have compiled extensive underwater acoustic data into a comprehensive dataset. Most existing research relies on optical sensors, which are limited by light scattering and attenuation in the water column, especially in high-turbidity environments. Multibeam echosounders (MBESs) can perceive the water column acoustically but most datasets in this domain are not public or lack the real-world complexity [5], [6].

Deep convolutional neural networks have proven effective in detection and classification tasks, but they often require extensive datasets to generalise well. A recent comprehensive overview of sonar-based deep learning in underwater robotics highlights that the predominant use of sonar is characterised by limited training data and inherent noise, which poses significant challenges to model robustness [7]. The authors identify the lack of baseline sonar-based datasets and a gap between simulation and reality, suggesting that establishing such datasets are critical for future research.

This is not the first dataset to study underwater marine litter, but it offers unexplored perspectives, especially regarding water column detection in active harbour environments with multiple acoustic frequencies. Some existing solutions rely on synthetic data generation through simulators [8] or generative adversarial networks (GANs) [9], [10], which, despite improvements, still exhibit notorious differences compared to real acoustic images [11]. Other datasets focus on controlled environments where small-scale datasets are collected from water tanks [6], [12], [13], [14].

More recently, Valdenegro-Toro et al. introduced the Marine Debris Forward-Looking Sonar (FLS) Datasets [15], which provides data from watertank, turntable, and flooded

quarry settings. Forward-Looking Multibeam—Marine Litter Detection and Tracking Dataset (FLM-MLDT) dataset differs by capturing data in the Leixões harbour manoeuvring basin that is a real-world, dynamic environment near the sea. Unlike datasets focused on the seafloor or static tanks, FLM-MLDT provides 8156 acoustic images specifically targeting the water column across ten different classes of debris including the nylon rope they are tethered with. The data is acquired at varying acoustic frequencies, and allows unique studies on the impact the acoustic frequency can have on detection, filling a critical gap in field measurements of submerged plastic debris [16].

COLLECTION METHODS AND DESIGN

The proposed dataset, FLM-MLDT, contains 8156 acoustic images acquired in the manoeuvring basin of Leixões harbour in Porto, Portugal ($41^{\circ}11'04.8''N$, $8^{\circ}42'22.0''W$), as represented and marked with a blue square in Fig. 1. The data acquisition campaign was conducted in waters with a depth ranging between 2.5 m and 10 m.

To ensure high-fidelity data suitable for robotic perception tasks, data collection was performed with PORTUS, a fully electric Unmanned Surface Vessel (USV) developed by the Centre of Robotics and Autonomous Systems (CRAS) that belongs to Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science (INESC TEC), illustrated in Fig. 2.

Robotic Platform and Sensor setup

PORTUS is a versatile USV platform utilised in this dataset campaign for its low acoustic signature. Powered by two stern-mounted electric Torqeedo motors, the vessel minimises noise interference, making it ideal for acoustic data acquisition. For navigation, the vessel integrates an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), a Real-Time Kinematic Global Navigation Satellite System (RTK-GNSS), and a Doppler Velocity Log (DVL), fused to provide 250 Hz high-precision localisation. The RTK-GNSS receiver is also responsible for providing the primary time reference for the onboard computer clock. In addition, a Pulse Per Sec (PPS) signal is used to prevent the clock drift between software synchronisation updates. As a result, the onboard computer acts as the central time authority for the rest of the platform. Sensors

FIG. 3. M3 MBES and camera installed in the PORTUS telescopic keel with a FLS configuration during (a) dataset collection and (b) their mounting point mechanical design.

supporting the software synchronisation timestamp their data directly using this shared time reference, preventing timing errors caused by transmission delays. For sensors that do not support software synchronisation, incoming data are timestamped upon arrival at the onboard computer.

For stability, PORTUS has a telescopic keel that enhances the vessel's hydrodynamic stability during operations and serves as the mounting point for underwater sensors. The primary sensor for the dataset campaign, Kongsberg M3 High-Frequency (HF) MBES [17], was installed on the telescopic keel of the vessel [Fig. 3(a)] at a depth of 1.5 m. Positioning the sensor below the waterline reduced surface disturbances such as waves and air bubbles. The MBES was fixed at a 25° physical tilt [Fig. 3(b)], providing a FLS configuration.

Sensor Configuration

Data were acquired in sequential runs using three distinct acoustic frequencies for each target: 950 kHz, 1200 kHz, and 1400 kHz. This approach allows for the analysis of the tradeoff between spatial resolution and field of view (FoV), as well as the reflectivity of each target when ensonified with different acoustic frequencies. The MBES settings were maintained with a fixed maximum range of 8 m for all trials to standardise the data, despite the ability to reach further distances. Doing so allowed to minimise noise from backscatter reflections at larger distances. The angular resolution (the angular space between beams) varies with frequency, as listed in Table II, as well as the FoV, which is lower the higher the acoustic frequency, since there is less spacing between each beam.

Note on 950 kHz Artifacts: Users may observe a shift in backscatter intensity in the 950 kHz imagery. This is a known instrumental artefact of the Kongsberg M3 system, resulting from transitions between internal transmit/receive frequency bands and associated gain corrections. It represents a system normalisation effect rather than a change in environmental properties.

While the Kongsberg M3 MBES relies on a proprietary Windows-based development kit (M3 2.5.4) for the sonar head configuration, beamforming computations and data processing, our collection architecture required integration with the Robot Operating System (ROS) to ensure synchronisation with the robotic platform, namely with its navigation data. To achieve this, an in-house driver was

TABLE I. Average M3 MBES Frame Rate Across Different Operating Frequencies During the Dataset Campaign

Operating Frequency (kHz)	Average Frame Rate
950	7.80
1200	8.80
1400	9.23
Overall	8.67

developed to interface directly with Kongsberg's Application Programming Interface (API).

This custom driver served two critical functions.

- 1) *Dynamic Reconfiguration:* It allowed for the on-the-fly reconfiguration of the sonar head, including changes to operating frequency and maximum range, directly from the ROS environment.
- 2) *Data Synchronisation:* By bridging the Windows-based sonar data with the ROS framework running on PORTUS, the driver enabled to record and to synchronise the acoustic images with the vessel's navigation data. The navigation and odometry data were acquired at a fixed sampling rate of 250 Hz, but the M3 MBES operated at a varying frame rate due to the high computational demand of processing raw acoustic data. The frequency-specific average frame rates achieved during the campaign are detailed in Table I.

To temporally align these data streams, a dedicated ROS synchronisation node was implemented with the `ApproximateTimeSynchronizer`. The node paired each acoustic image frame with the most temporally proximate high-frequency navigation message. An analysis across the 33 synchronised sequences, confirmed an accurate temporal alignment with an average synchronisation error of 13.61 ms between the acoustic frames and the navigation odometry. This synchronisation ensures that the robotic platform's pose is reliably mapped to the sonar imagery for subsequent detection and tracking tasks.

These functions are operated through PORTUS main processing unit based in an Unix architecture, which is connected via Ethernet to the M3 dedicated computer.

To ensure dataset consistency and comparability across frequencies, the Time Variant Gain (TVG) parameters (A, B, C, and L) were kept constant throughout the entire campaign.

The complete set of acoustic configurations and specifications is detailed in Table II. Note that the angular resolution is derived from the ratio of the FoV to the number of beams.

Marine Litter Selected Targets and Deployment

Targets were deployed in the water column using an auxiliary boat provided by INESC TEC—EPISEA, which also served as the remote control station for the PORTUS USV to ensure precise manoeuvring. Objects were tethered to a buoy and a

TABLE II. MBES Configurations and Specifications for Each Operating Frequency

Parameter	Operating Frequency		
	950 kHz	1200 kHz	1400 kHz
FoV	140°	75°	45°
Angular Resolution	0.55°	0.29°	0.18°
Maximum Range	8 m		
Beams	256		
Samples per Beam	2042		
Pulse Type	CW and Chirp Modulation		
TVG A	20		
TVG B	100		
TVG C	-8		
TVG L	100		
Image Gain	10		
Gain Threshold	140		

FIG. 4. Target placement with a buoy and PORTUS at the manoeuvring basin of Leixões harbour.

weight via nylon rope to maintain a consistent depth of 5 m (Fig. 4).

The surface buoy provided a visual ground truth, facilitating the localisation of submerged targets during acoustic acquisition. The USV executed various manoeuvring patterns to vary the range and bearing relative to the targets with sequences made with each of the three acoustic frequencies. This approach resulted in a dataset where acoustic footprints change significantly across frames, providing multiple view-points of the same object and simulating a realistic approach to submerged debris.

The dataset captures ten distinct categories of marine litter, including the nylon rope itself, which serves as both a tether and a target class, as it is a common form of marine litter making the dataset composed of Eleven different categories of marine litter. Each of those categories has a specific class identification (ID), and each object is detailed in Table III and illustrated in Fig. 5. The selection strategy prioritised material diversity to represent objects typically found in aquatic environments, ranging from metals and woods to varied synthetic polymers, as is the case of the Polyethylene (PE), Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) and vinyl. Deliberately, several selected objects share similar geometric shapes. This design choice challenges detection algorithms

TABLE III. Selected Marine Debris Objects With Their Corresponding Class Names, Class Identification, Material Composition and Dimension

Class Name	ID	Material	Dimensions (m)
Aluminium tube	0	Aluminium	$H = 0.39$ $R = 0.04$
Fish net	1	Nylon, foam, PVC buoys	Undisclosed
Floating wood floor	2	High density fibreboard	$L = 0.20$ $W = 0.20$
Plastic deck	3	Polyethylene	$L = 0.30$ $W = 0.30$
PVC cone	4	Wood-plastic composite	Base: $L = 0.22$, $W = 0.22$, $H = 0.36$
PVC perforated deck	5	PVC	$L = 0.56$ $W = 0.56$
PVC Square	6	Transparent PVC	$L = 0.50$ $W = 0.50$
Vinyl	7	Vinyl	$L = 0.49$ $W = 0.62$
Wooden deck	8	Wood	$L = 0.30$ $W = 0.30$
PVC Blue Square	9	Opaque PVC	$L = 0.50$ $W = 0.50$
Rope	10	Nylon	$R = 0.005$

Note: H refers to height, L to length, W to width and R to radius.

to distinguish targets based on their acoustic reflectivity and material properties rather than geometric shape alone.

Two specific classes require distinct notation.

- 1) *Fish Net (ID 1)*: This target represents a complex agglomerate of nylon mesh, foam, and PVC buoys, mimicking real-world ghost nets which are difficult to characterise with standard dimensions.
- 2) *Rope (ID 10)*: The nylon rope used to tether the objects is visible in the acoustic imagery. It is annotated as a distinct class because rope segments are a prevalent form of marine litter.

Because the dataset was collected in a real-world harbour environment, it includes frames devoid of targets, as well as background noise generated by marine wildlife and the environment itself. Including these elements is essential for training robust detection algorithms.

Data Processing and Formats

Following acquisition via the ROS interface, the dataset backscatter data was processed into three complementary formats after being stored in `pointcloud2` ROS message format, as represented in Fig. 6. The acoustic intensities mapped to these formats are inherently normalised by the

FIG. 5. Dataset marine debris selected objects.

FIG. 6. Acoustic image representations with the fish net target based on the same acquired frame. (a) Raw format. (b) Polar format. (c) Cartesian format. All the formats are represented with the correspondent axis with values for better interpretation.

sonar head. The format denominations are derived from the spatial transformation applied to the acoustic backscatter data.

- 1) *Raw*: A direct matrix representation of the beam intensity values ($256 \text{ beams} \times 2042 \text{ bins}$), useful for low-level signal analysis without geometric correction and real-time visualisation in the field, is illustrated in Fig. 6(a).
- 2) *Polar*: A geometrically transformed representation mapping the data to Angle (θ) and Range (r), often used for efficient obstacle detection, is represented in Fig. 6(b).
- 3) *Cartesian*: A top-down mosaic representing the true geometry of the scene. To generate these images from the sparse angular data, a Gaussian kernel (size 21) was applied to populate the pixel neighbourhood, filling the gaps between beams to create a coherent spatial map, is illustrated in Fig. 6(c).

The *raw image* is classified as nongeometric because it serves as a direct visualisation of the sensor’s memory buffer rather than a spatial map. While this representation can correlate to physical properties, the visualisation ignores the angular separation between beams. Physically, acoustic beams fan out radially from the sensor origin. The raw image renders them as parallel columns in a rectangular matrix. Consequently, a linear feature in the physical world (such as a flat wall) appears curved (hyperbolic) in this projection, as the time-of-flight differs for central versus peripheral beams striking the same planar surface.

The *polar image* maps acoustic data into a coordinate system where the horizontal axis corresponds to the scan angle (θ) and the vertical axis to the range (r). While this format preserves the raw topological structure of the sensor data, it introduces geometric distortion when rendered on a rectilinear pixel grid. The processed image has a constant pixel width to every beam regardless of distance. Consequently, objects at close range appear horizontally stretched, while those at far range appear horizontally compressed, as the visualization does not account for the radial divergence of the acoustic energy. To ensure compatibility with object detection, which require fixed input tensor dimensions, the dataset enforces spatial consistency. Despite the varying physical FoV across different acoustic frequencies, the processing pipeline restricts the generated images to a fixed angular range of 45° , determined by the minimum FoV presented in Table II. By maintaining fixed range and FoV within this constrained window, the resulting image dimensions remain constant, ensuring a standardised input for the detection models.

The *cartesian image* is constructed via a coordinate transformation that maps the polar sensor data (r, θ) onto a standard Euclidean grid (x, y) using the transformation

$$x = r \cos \theta, \quad y = r \sin \theta. \quad (1)$$

This process, often referred to as scan conversion, corrects the angular divergence of the beams. The output pixel resolu-

tion (meters/pixel) is computed dynamically for each frame to satisfy the Nyquist criterion, defined as half the minimum physical distance between adjacent acoustic samples.

To address the nonuniform sampling density where data points are dense near the origin and sparse at maximum range the Gaussian kernel interpolation. A kernel size of 21 was empirically chosen to closely match native hardware representations while minimising the introduction of artificial data artifacts. Because this approach accumulates overlapping additive weights, it does not conserve total acoustic energy. It enhances the visual contrast of the targets, ensuring that the resulting map accurately preserves the shape, orientation, and relative scale of physical objects being a typically representation used by human operators.

VALIDATION AND QUALITY

To ensure the reliability and utility of the FLM-MLDT dataset for learning-based applications, a comprehensive quality control and validation process was undertaken. This involved assessing the acoustic signal integrity, verifying annotation accuracy against physical ground truth, and establishing baseline detection benchmarks using state-of-the-art deep learning models.

Acoustic Data Quality and Anomalies

The dataset captures the acoustic complexity of a real-world harbour environment. Unlike synthetic data or controlled water tank experiments, these images contain backscatter from biological activity (wildlife), water column turbulence, and suspended particulate matter. Those act as a source of noise, but they were retained in the dataset to accurately reflect the sensor's raw output. This presents a realistic challenge for normalisation algorithms, preventing models from over-fitting to idealised sonar data.

Frames without targets, designated as background frames, were included in the dataset due to their significance for object detection and tracking tasks. These frames enable models to characterise the harbour's inherent acoustic variance, thereby reducing the likelihood of false positives. In addition, the presence of marine life, that was validated visually during the campaign, serves as a natural distractor class. Furthermore, these sequences are essential for evaluating the robustness of tracking algorithms, particularly in scenarios involving occlusion or targets exiting the FoV.

The primary challenge in underwater acoustic datasets are establishing ground truth: confirming that a specific acoustic footprint corresponds to a specific object. We addressed this through the physical tethering setup described in the deployment section.

The surface buoy served as a visual marker, allowing the annotators to correlate the USV's relative position with the target's known location.

Baseline Detection Benchmarks

To demonstrate the dataset's suitability for developing automatic target detection pipelines, we performed baseline experiments using the You Only Look Once version 8 (YOLOv8) architecture. This model was selected for its prevalence in real-time robotic applications. We evaluated two model variants: YOLOv8n (nano) and YOLOv8m (medium) to assess performance across different computational complexities.

Training was performed on an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 SUPER Graphics Processing Unit (GPU). All models were trained for a maximum of 200 epochs, incorporating an early stopping mechanism with a patience of 50 epochs to prevent large training times without improvements, with an input image size of 640×640 pixels and a batch size of twelve. To improve convergence and regularisation, the AdamW optimiser was applied with an initial learning rate of 0.001, weight decay of 0.0001, and momentum of 0.937.

The annotated polar images were split into training, validation and testing sets. The dataset splitting preserves the temporal continuity of the test sequences, while introducing randomness on the rest of the frames. A standard random train-test split at the frame level would fragment trajectories and introduce data leakage. A contiguous sequence comprising 20% of each video was isolated exclusively for the test set. To prevent the selection of empty sequences where tracking cannot occur, a class-aware sliding window algorithm was implemented. This algorithm traversed the entire video to identify the continuous block of frames containing the highest density of tracking targets. Furthermore, to prevent the test set from depleting the training data, a constraint was applied to ensure that a minimum of 40% of the target instances remained outside the test window. Once the sequential test block was isolated and exported as a continuous video, the remaining frames were randomly shuffled and split into training (90%) and validation (10%) sets, providing the detector with diverse, uncorrelated data during the learning phase. All frames were annotated and converted to the YOLOv8 labelling format.

Common augmentation strategies such as mosaicking, MixUp, vertical flipping, and hue/saturation colour shifts were disabled, since they violate the geometric constraints and single-channel intensity properties of FLS acoustic data. Augmentations included horizontal flipping, random rotations, scaling, and spatial translation and random intensity shifting, the latter being applied to simulate varying acoustic gain and depth attenuation, alongside random erasing to mimic acoustic shadowing and signal occlusion in the water column. These augmentations are not detailed in the *Data Processing* section. This exclusion is intentional, as the published FLM-MLDT dataset contains only the original acoustic imagery, leaving augmentation as a dynamic step for the training pipeline.

The benchmark has considered multiple metrics, based on the precision (P), recall (R), and mean average precision

TABLE IV. Benchmark of the YOLOv8 Custom Trained Models

Freq	P	R	mAP ₅₀	mAP _{50:95}	AP _{AT}	AP _{FN}	AP _{FWB}	AP _{PD}	AP _C	AP _{PF}	AP _{PS}	AP _V	AP _{WD}	AP _{PSO}	AP _R	Params
<i>YOLOv8 nano</i>																
950 kHz	0.46	0.41	0.39	0.11	-	0.90	0.04	0.27	-	-	0.30	0.15	0.62	0.30	0.38	3 M
1200 kHz	0.63	0.48	0.52	0.16	0.50	0.46	0.37	0.35	0.15	0.72	0.22	0.58	0.36	0.63	0.61	
1400 kHz	0.57	0.51	0.50	0.19	0.52	0.68	0.14	0.16	0.96	0.76	0.72	0.38	0.99	0.28	0.36	
<i>YOLOv8 medium</i>																
950 kHz	0.50	0.42	0.40	0.11	-	0.92	0.04	0.36	-	-	0.40	0.23	0.51	0.35	0.39	25.84 M
1200 kHz	0.62	0.51	0.55	0.18	0.44	0.48	0.49	0.54	0.20	0.76	0.16	0.64	0.38	0.60	0.62	
1400 kHz	0.58	0.52	0.53	0.20	0.41	0.61	0.19	0.18	0.93	0.78	0.73	0.54	0.99	0.30	0.40	

Note: The aluminium tube AP (AP_{AT}), the fish net AP (AP_{FN}), the floating wood board AP (AP_{FWB}), the plastic deck AP (AP_{PD}), the PVC cone AP (AP_C), the perforated deck AP (AP_{PF}), the PVC square AP (AP_{PS}), the vinyl AP (AP_V), the wooden deck AP (AP_{WD}), the opaque PVC square AP (AP_{PSO}) and the rope AP (AP_R).

FIG. 7. Dataset benchmark overall metrics for each model.

(mAP) to measure the accuracy of detectors. The intersection over union (IoU) value was also considered as the area of overlap between the detected bounding box and the labelled ground truth. The mAP:50 considers a IoU of 0.5 whereas the mAP50:95 is a more comprehensive evaluation metric. It calculates the average precision across multiple IoU thresholds, ranging from 0.50 to 0.95 in steps of 0.05. The average precision (AP) per class was considered. The model size, based on the parameters, was extracted. The benchmark details are listed in Table IV and the main results can be visualised in Fig. 7. Benchmarks indicate that the dataset supports convergence for object detection models. The 1200 kHz frequency provided the highest detection accuracy, representing the optimal tradeoff between spatial resolution and signal-to-noise ratio. Models with larger backbones achieved better generalisation.

RECORDS AND STORAGE

The dataset is publicly available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18235788>). It contains four separate .zip files. The dataset is distributed in four compressed archives: annotations_navigation.zip, cartesian.zip, polar.zip, and raw.zip. To reconstruct the directory structure described in this study, users should first extract annotations_navigation.zip, which will generate the annotations, navigation, and ros_navigation_bags directories. Subsequently, a new directory named images should be created at the root

level. The contents of the remaining three archives (cartesian.zip, polar.zip, and raw.zip) must be extracted inside this images directory. The final structure will appear as follows.

```
Dataset/
|-- annotations/
|-- navigation/
|-- ros_navigation_bags/
`-- images/
    |-- cartesian/
    |-- polar/
    `-- raw/
```

It contains a total of 8156 image files for each of the three acoustic representations (Raw, Polar, and Cartesian), stored in Portable Network Graphics (PNG) format.

During the experimental campaign, the raw acoustic data feed was monitored in real-time to identify the acoustic footprints of the targets. The low-latency output of the raw format was critical for operational decision-making, as the live visualisation of these footprints served as the primary trigger to initiate data acquisition for each specific target at each acoustic frequency. This real-time monitoring allowed for immediate cross-referencing of acoustic returns with the mission logs and ROS bag timestamps, which documented the precise start of each acquisition sequence. Since each target was tethered and buoy-marked individually, acoustic footprints were identified based on their spatiotemporal consistency with deployment logs and the expected geometry of the known targets, effectively distinguishing them from transient environmental noise or local wildlife.

The annotation process was conducted using the Label Studio platform providing a centralised environment for multi-user collaboration. Bounding boxes were manually drawn in the polar image format, selected because it preserves the inherent range and bearing geometry essential for subsequent detection and tracking solutions. A multistage validation protocol was implemented. Initial annotations were performed by a primary expert (P.G.). Following this initial curation, a peer-verification phase was conducted to minimise subjective bias where three researchers (M.L., P.M., and

FIG. 8. Class distribution per frequency.

H.M.S.) performed a frame-by-frame audit of the sequences to confirm target presence and boundary accuracy.

A target was annotated only if its acoustic footprint was distinct from the tether rope and consistent with the known geometry of the object. In cases of ambiguity or low acoustic contrast, such as the aluminium tube and PVC cone at 950 kHz, no bounding boxes were generated to prevent the introduction of noisy labels into the dataset. Disputed frames were resolved through a consensus-based review involving all authors, ensuring a multiple interpretation of the acquired data. This structured collaboration between primary annotation and independent validation served as our inter-annotator agreement framework.

The resulting annotations were converted from the platform’s native percentage-based coordinates to the standard YOLOv8 format using normalised coordinates ($xywh$), defined as follows.

- 1) *Normalisation*: All values are normalised between 0 and 1 relative to the total width and height of the image.
- 2) *Centroid Reference*: The x and y coordinates refer to the *center* of the bounding box, rather than the top-left corner.
- 3) *File Structure*: Each image has a corresponding plain text file (`.txt`) where each line represents a single object, formatted as:

```
<class_id> <x_center> <y_center>
<width> <height>.
```

The class distribution of the selected marine debris for each acoustic frequency type, based on the polar acoustic image annotations, is shown in Fig. 8. Since the dataset was made to be extensive to different tasks, many of the extracted frames may not contain the selected marine debris. The rope has more occurrences since it was used to tether all the targets, appearing in more frames.

Data Organisation

The general directory structure follows a nested structure, with the root directory containing four primary folders: `annotations`, `images`, `navigation`, and `ros_navigation_bags`. An overview of this organisation is visualised in Fig. 9.

For users that do not use ROS, it was ensured precise temporal synchronisation between acoustic data and navigation telemetry, since each message in the CSV file share a common timestamp convention in with the images filenames. For each frame, independent of image format, the images will have a filename similar to the following.

```
image_YYYY-MM-DD_HH-MM-SS.millisecond.png
```

The `images` directory is divided into three sub-folders representing the acoustic formats: `cartesian`, `polar`, and `raw`. Inside each format folder, the structure is subdivided by *target class* and subsequently by *acoustic frequency* (950, 1200, and 1400 kHz).

- 1) *Suffix Note*: Some frequency folders may contain a numerical suffix (e.g., `1400_1`). This notation indicates distinct acquisition runs extracted at different time frames, which is critical for users developing applications that require sequential continuity. It is important to note that while the image data is physically organised into distinct folders based on acquisition sequences (e.g., separate acquisition runs for the same frequency), the annotation process was conducted uniformly across the entire dataset. Every annotated frame has a corresponding text file in the `annotations` directory, regardless of the sequence split. There is no gap in labelling logic between sequences. Users can therefore merge these sequences into a single large dataset for training.

The `annotations` directory mirrors the structure of the `images` folder and contains.

- 1) *Format*: Plain text files (`.txt`) following the YOLOv8 specification.
- 2) *Configuration*: A `data_config.yaml` file is included to facilitate immediate training.
- 3) *Usage Recommendation*: It is strongly recommended to train models within the same acoustic frequency domain. Cross-frequency training (e.g., training on 950 kHz and testing on 1200 kHz) may yield suboptimal results due to the varying resolution and signal-to-noise characteristics [18].

To support localisation and mapping tasks, the `navigation` directory contains parsed navigation data in CSV format, organised by Target and Frequency. Unlike the `images` folder, which contain thousands of files, each `navigation` folder contains four specific summary files.

```
marimar_nav_local.csv
```

This is the primary telemetry file, containing synchronized odometry messages matched to each

FIG. 9. Directory tree describing the dataset organization.

acoustic image. It provides the high-frequency state estimation of the USV.

- 1) `matched_image`: The specific filename (e.g., `image_...png`) corresponding to the telemetry row.
- 2) `pose.pose`: The estimated three-dimensional (3D) position (x, y, z) and orientation (quaternion x, y, z, w) in the local fixed frame (`world_ned`).
- 3) `twist.twist`: The instantaneous linear (v_x, v_y, v_z) and angular ($\omega_x, \omega_y, \omega_z$) velocities.

`gps_fix2.csv`

Contains the Global Positioning System (GPS) coordinates of the local fixed frame (`world_ned`). The values are constant as the frame is the same across all data collection.

`tf.csv`

Stores dynamic ROS transform (TF) messages that describe the platform's motion over time.

- 1) `transforms`: A serialised text block containing the translation vector and rotation quaternion defining the relationship between the global frame (`world_ned`) and the robot base frame (`body_marimar`) at the specific timestamp.

`tf_static.csv`

Defines the fixed physical layout (extrinsics) of the sensors installed in the platform, which remains constant throughout the mission.

- 1) `transforms`: Contains the static spatial transformations (translations and rotations) between the robot base and its sensors (e.g., `body_marimar` \rightarrow `m3_rot_link`). This file effectively defines the 3D frame of the robotic platform.

For users familiar with ROS, we provide the navigation bag files. These files contain the navigation streams for each acquisition run, enabling playback of the mission data in a native ROS environment. The navigation-related ROS topics

were synchronised with their corresponding timestamps, and the acoustic images acquired with the MBES.

INSIGHTS AND NOTES

This dataset presents specific characteristics and challenges that potential users must consider to maximise the data's utility beyond standard object detection.

A key insight from our baseline validation is the significant impact of acoustic frequency on detection reliability. The dataset is organised into continuous acquisition runs, and the navigation files provide high-frequency odometry synchronised with the acoustic frames. Researchers can use this temporal coherence to develop tracking algorithms. Correlating the USV's motion with shifts in target coordinates in polar imagery, Kalman Filters or Transformer-based trackers can be trained to maintain target ID across occlusions.

Real-world harbour environments are noisy. The dataset deliberately includes frames containing biological noise (e.g., fish schools), wake turbulence from the support vessel, and the tethering ropes. Users can use frames without target-class annotations as negative samples to train networks to ignore transient acoustic noise, a critical requirement for autonomous operation in the wild.

Limitations and Future Work

This dataset represents a significant step toward autonomous marine litter detection, but has several limitations that could serve as future research topics. The dataset's diversity could be broader, as the current collection focuses on Eleven specific classes of relatively large marine debris. Future campaigns aim to expand this catalogue to include smaller litter items such as bottles, aluminium cans, and plastic bags, while also extending data collection to open-sea scenarios where wave dynamics and seabed topology differ significantly. Similarly, to ensure that detection algorithms do not overfit to the specific acoustic signature or motion characteristics of a single vessel, future work should consider using multiple sonars and robotic platforms, including Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs).

SOURCE CODE AND SCRIPTS

Data extraction was performed using the Kongsberg M3 Sonar API (version 2.5.4) [19] and the underlying ROS nodes were developed at INESC TEC, including the extraction and synchronisation nodes. For simplification purposes, our dataset already provides acoustic data in three image formats, without pre or postprocessing pipelines. This approach ensures a neutral baseline, allowing researchers full autonomy to implement and test their own processing algorithms on the acoustic images.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Pedro Alves Guedes (P.G.) and Maksym Lysak (M.L.) wrote the manuscript. P.G. and Pedro Martins (P.M.) were responsible for data recording and extraction. P.G. annotated and curated the data, while M.L., P.M., and Hugo Miguel Silva (H.M.S.) performed annotation validation. P.G., M.L., Guilherme Amaral (G.A.), P.M., and Carlos Almeida (C.A.) contributed to mechanical integration and design. M.L. and C.A. managed target displacement, with G.A. and C.A. performing USV and support vessel piloting. P.G. and Sen Wang (S.W.) handled benchmarking and technical validation. H.M.S., Alfredo Martins (A.M.), and José Miguel Almeida (J.M.A.) defined the project scope. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

The authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

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